

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D3.5

Establishment of the External
Advisory Board

September 2021

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
EAB	External Advisory Board
PC	Project Coordinator
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1 EXTERNAL ADVISORY BOARD

As described in the WP3 and included in the deliverables D3.1 and D3.2, an External Advisory Board (EAB) has been appointed, consisting of 10 members.

The Expert Advisory Board (EAB) draws on the wider stakeholder community including international experts and other major stakeholders in the ecosystem the project is focusing on, in order to supplement MES-CoBraD Consortium expertise and provide advice throughout different stages of the MES-CoBraD development and implementation.

The MES-CoBraD Consortium ensures the legitimacy and transparency of the selection process of these experts. Each partner of the MES-CoBraD Consortium nominated suitable candidates taking into account that these candidates are high-calibre international experts, external to the MES-CoBraD Consortium and are willing to and suitable to assist in project decisions of strategic nature, provide advice to technical and scientific issues within key issues and deliverables and support the dissemination activities of the project. All suggestions were collected by the Project Coordinator and discussed in the General Assembly. The selected candidates were contacted by an official invitation, in order to confirm their interest and further engagement in the activities of MES-CoBraD EAB. The MES-CoBraD Consortium has reserved the needed financial resources (under travel costs of the Project Coordinator) to support the travel needs of the EAB members. Their selection was based on their proven expertise in the field of this project, their commitment to the project, their expected contribution to the success of the project, and their ability to strengthen the visibility of the project.

The EAB sole purpose will be to ensure the project's alignment and commitment to its preliminary goals and expectations. The EAB will provide input on task and deliverable quality, verifying the project is on track with its objectives. The EAB will provide an unbiased perspective on the developed protocols, their implementation and reaching of milestones towards achieving the overarching project goals. The EAB will continue to follow project progress and supply with feedback every six months during the pilot implementation (WP8).

An Expert Agreement and a Non-disclosure Agreement are executed between all partners and each EAB member before the onset of the EAB activities and before any confidential information is exchanged.

1.1 EAB MEMBERS

1.1.1 RICARDO OSORIO (ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR, DEPARTMENT OF PSYCHIATRY, NEW YORK UNIVERSITY GROSSMAN SCHOOL OF MEDICINE)

Dr. Osorio is a member of the Nathan S. Kline Institute for Psychiatric Research and the NYU Langone Medical Center where he is a faculty member. At NYU, he recently inaugurated the Sleep, Aging and Memory (SAM) Lab in collaboration with the Mount Sinai Integrative Sleep Center (formerly NYU Sleep Disorders Center). He also works at NYU's Center for Brain Health (CBH) and is the Clinical Director of the Multicultural Program at the Alzheimer's Disease Center. Born in Madrid, Spain, he earned his medical degree at the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. He completed his residency in psychiatry at the Hospital 12 de Octubre and completed an internship in neuropsychiatry at the Institute of Neurology, Queen's Square (UK). During his residency, he completed a Master's in neuropsychology at the Universidad Complutense de Madrid. Dr. Osorio developed his professional career in Spain as a geriatric psychiatrist and worked as a research scientist in the Alzheimer's Project Research Unit (CIEN Foundation, Spain) until 2009. He was then recruited by CBH at the NYU School of Medicine, and after 7 years at NYU by NKI's Clinical Research Division. His area of research interest is the use of neuroimaging and cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers to assist in the study of sleep disturbances as risk factors for cognitive

impairment in aging and for dementia.

1.1.2 GONZALO ALARCON (PROFESSOR OF NEUROLOGY WEILL-CORNELL MEDICAL COLLEGE, DOHA, QATAR; SENIOR CONSULTANT EPILEPTOLOGIST)

Dr. Alarcon graduated in Medicine with distinction (“Premio Extraordinario”) in 1984, and obtained a PhD from the Universidad Complutense. In 1987, he obtained a Fleming Award to carry out research on spinal processing of pain in the Department of Physiology of the University of Bristol (UK). He specialised in Clinical Neurophysiology in the UK. Over the last 20 years, his clinical practice has focused on electroencephalography, presurgical assessment of epilepsy, telemetry, intracranial recordings and intra-operative electrocorticography. Such clinical practice has provided the basis for research on several aspects of epileptology at Imperial College, at Universidad Complutense and at King’s College Hospital, with particular interest in presurgical assessment of epilepsy and the mechanisms involved in the generation and propagation of human epileptiform discharges and seizures. Some of the research techniques developed by his group have translated into clinically useful tests (single pulse electrical stimulation, discharge latency analysis). In 1994, he was awarded the Gowers Prize (Young Physician) by the International League against Epilepsy (British Branch). He run the MSc Course in Epilepsy since 1995 until 2015, and he is the lead editor of the Epilepsy volume of the Oxford Specialist Handbooks in Neurology (2009). He has led most research in epilepsy surgery and video monitoring at King’s College London over the last 20 years and has over 200 publications in the field of EEG and epilepsy. He served as Consultant in Clinical Neurophysiology at King’s College Hospital from 1996 to 2015 and Reader at the Institute of Psychiatry from 2009 until 2015. In October 2015, he moved to Doha (Qatar) as a Senior Consultant Epileptologist for Hamad Medical Corporation. He has been a Professor of Neurology at Weill-Cornell Medical College since December 2017.

1.1.3 DAVID TANNE (PROFESSOR OF NEUROLOGY, DIRECTOR OF STROKE AND COGNITION INSTITUTE AT THE RAMBAM HEALTH CARE CAMPUS)

Prof. David Tanne serves as the president of the Israel Neurological Association. He is a Professor of Neurology and directs the Stroke and Cognition Institute at the Rambam Health Care Campus. A graduate of the Sackler Faculty of Medicine (Magna cum laude), he completed his fellowship in stroke and cerebrovascular diseases during 1996-1998 at the Henry Ford Hospital and Health Sciences Center, Detroit Campus of Case Western University, Detroit, USA. Prof. Tanne has directed the Stroke Center at the Sheba Medical Center and served at the Sackler Faculty of Medicine, Tel Aviv University, and has been staff at the interdisciplinary Sagol School of Neuroscience and the Herczeg Institute on Aging. He initiated reperfusion therapy for acute ischemic stroke in Israel, established a dedicated stroke unit, a neurovascular ultrasound lab and stroke prevention clinics. Prof. Tanne is a principal Investigator of the National Acute Stroke Israeli Registry (NASIS) Project, the chair of the advisory committee for the Israeli Stroke Register, Israeli Ministry of Health, and Member of National Council of Heart and Vascular Disease, the Israeli National Health Councils. He has published over 250 scientific peer reviewed publications, serves on the editorial board of the journal Stroke and his major areas of interest are stroke, vascular cognitive impairment, dementia and Alzheimer disease, novel technologies and brain health.

1.1.4 LOGAN SCHNEIDER (CLINICAL ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, STANFORD SLEEP CENTER; CO-DIRECTOR, STANFORD/VA ALZHEIMER'S RESEARCH CENTER)

Logan Schneider, M.D., is a Consultant Neurologist at the Palo Alto VA Health Care System. He has been interested in caring for patients with neurocognitive disorders (e.g., Alzheimer disease) since his medical school training in the North Florida-South Georgia VA Health Care System under the inspirational cognitive neurologist Dr. Kenneth Heilman. Dr. Schneider’s passion for improving care through communication is

reflected in his numerous community outreach endeavors. Through a multidisciplinary care approach that involves educating at all levels – patients, families, caregivers, and care providers – he hopes to incorporate cutting-edge science to changing the course of these life-altering disorders. Moreover, Dr. Logan Schneider specializes in the treatment of sleep disorders, which include sleep apnea, narcolepsy, insomnia, restless legs syndrome, sleepwalking, and REM-sleep behavior disorder. He has practiced Sleep Neurology for more than 5 years. Dr. Schneider has a special interest in REM-sleep behavior disorder and other parasomnias (such as sleepwalking).

1.1.5 DIMITRIOS ARKILLO (NEUROLOGIST-EPILEPTOLOGIST; VICE PRESIDENT OF CLINICAL DEVELOPMENT RARE DISEASE, ACADIA PHARMACEUTICALS)

Dr. Dimitrios Arkillo is a pediatrician, neurologist, and epileptologist with interest in rare neurological disorders. Dr. Arkillo is Vice-President of Clinical Development Rare Diseases, at Acadia Pharmaceuticals. Prior to joining Acadia, Dr. Arkillo was a global clinical leader and executive medical director at Takeda Pharmaceuticals, and he led multiple clinical trials. Prior to Takeda, he was medical director at Sage Therapeutics, and he supported the phase 3 studies in super-refractory status epilepticus and in post-partum depression. Clinically, Dr. Arkillo has practiced at the Minnesota Epilepsy Group, where he served as principal and sub-investigator in its clinical research division for multiple industry sponsored phase 2-3 trials and established the first chromosome 15 duplication (Dup15q) clinic in Minnesota. Dr. Arkillo received his medical degree at Semmelweis University and trained at Winthrop University Hospital, Tufts University Hospital, and the University of Minnesota.

1.1.6 PHIL TITTENSOR (NURSE PROFESSIONAL– EPILEPSY; CHAIRPERSON, EPILEPSY NURSES ASSOCIATION [ESNA])

Phil Tittensor is Consultant Nurse for the Epilepsies, based in Wolverhampton. He is a Registered Nurse for people with Learning Disabilities (RNMH) and holds a Diploma in Nursing (DipN), a Master's Degree in epilepsy (MSc) and is a nurse independent prescriber (NIP). He qualified in 1990 and has worked with people who have epilepsy all of his career. He began his first Epilepsy Specialist Nursing post in 2000 and has worked exclusively with people who have epilepsy since then. His clinical work is with adults, but he still retains an interest in learning disabilities & runs a specialist epilepsy and learning disabilities clinic. Fifty percent of his current role involves research, teaching, and service development. He is principal investigator for several studies and has a particular interest in non-epileptic attack disorder (NEAD).

1.1.7 SUSAN REILLY (ASSOCIATE LIBRARIAN, UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN)

Susan Reilly is Associate Librarian for Collections and Archives at University College Dublin. She is actively engaged in copyright and open access related issues at international level and is member of the IFLA Committee for Copyright and Other Legal Matters, a co-chair of the IFLA Open Access Task Force. In Ireland, she co-chairs the National Open Research Framework Open Access Steering Committee and is Deputy Chair of the Consortium of National and University Libraries Regulatory Affairs Committee. Educated in Ireland, Ms. Reilly has a BA (Hons) in Information and Library Studies and Art History from the University of Wales in Aberystwyth, Wales, and an MSc in Information Management from the University of Sheffield.

1.1.8 FEDERICO SARTORE (TECHNOLOGY AND DATA PROTECTION LAWYER, CO-CHAIR OF THE INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF PRIVACY PROFESSIONAL (IAPP) FOR ITALY)

Federico Sartore is a lawyer specialized in the field IT and Technology Law, in particular with regard to Privacy & Data Protection aspects. Other main areas of activity consist in Cybersecurity, e-Identification and trust services, as well as technological development of undertakings. He regularly assists important national companies and multinational groups in structuring and managing complex personal data flows and architectures, advanced marketing and profiling programs, implementation of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence technologies, smart environments projects, biometrics data used for facilitative purposes. He also actively participated in specific projects in banking and finance, biomedical, media, prize draws and competitions, and telecommunications. Associate and then Senior Associate of Panetta & Associati, Federico cooperates with the LawTech research group of Trento University and attends as speaker conferences and seminars on European Data Protection Law and legal issues of Big Data technologies. He currently provides his contribution to several law reviews and journals. He graduated with the thesis “Big Data: Privacy and Intellectual Property in a comparative perspective”. The thesis granted him the 1st price for the call IEEE Smart Cities Trento 2015. He is currently PhD student at Maastricht University, working on a research project on risk and risk management in the field of data protection law.

1.1.9 STEFANIA ILINCA (POLICY ANALYST AND RESEARCHER, EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND RESEARCH)

Ștefania Ilinca is a researcher and policy analyst focused on understanding the effects of demographic aging on health and social policy in Europe, including patterns of use of care among the elderly. She received a master’s degree in Public Management from Bocconi University and holds a PhD in Health Economics. She is a senior researcher at the European Centre for Social Welfare Policy and Research in Vienna (UN affiliated) and regularly consults for the WHO, the World Bank and the European Commission. Her research focuses on highlighting persistent discrimination and inequity in access to health and long-term care, with particular attention to intersecting inequalities and vulnerable population groups. Through this work, she aims to inform policies for health and social care systems in Europe and beyond.

1.1.10 HAYIT GREENSPAN (PROFESSOR OF BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING AT TEL AVIV UNIVERSITY)

Professor Greenspan heads the Medical Image Processing and Analysis Lab at the Biomedical Engineering Department in the Faculty of Engineering, Tel-Aviv University. Professor Greenspan has been conducting research in image processing and computer vision for the past 20 years, with a special focus on deep learning, image modelling and analysis, resolution augmentation, and content-based image retrieval. She received her B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees in Electrical Engineering from the Technion Israel Institute of Technology, in 1986 and 1989, respectively, and her Ph.D. degree in Electrical Engineering from California Institute of Technology in 1994. She was a Postdoc with the Computer Science Division at U.C. Berkeley from 1995 to 1997. In 1997 she joined Tel-Aviv University. From 2008 until 2011, Professor Greenspan was a visiting Professor at Stanford University, Department of Radiology, Faculty of Medicine. She was also a visiting researcher at IBM Research in the Multi-modal Mining for Healthcare group, in Almaden CA. She is now also affiliated with the Computer Science Institute (ICSI) at Berkeley, CA. She is the inventor of several patents. She is an Associate Editor of the top-ranking journal in medical imaging (IEEE-TMI) and is an active member of several international professional societies.

1.2 EAB MEETINGS AND REPORTS

The EAB will meet biannually on occasion of one of the Consortium’s plenary meetings and will be required to consult on specific topics. The Project Coordinator will write the minutes of the EAB meetings and prepare the implementation of the EAB’s suggestions. The EAB members are allowed to participate in General Assembly meetings upon invitation but have no voting rights.

The MES-CoBraD Consortium and the WP Leaders will provide deliverables for review to the relevant members of the EAB prior to the submission of the deliverables and the EAB members’ comments will be attached to the deliverable as an ANNEX.

The plan for the EAB meetings and reviewed deliverables is as follows in Table 1.

Table 1. Meetings of the EAB

Meeting	Date	Deliverables
1 st Meeting	November 2021	D1.2; D2.1; D8.1
2 nd Meeting	March 2022	D2.3; D4.2; D8.3
3 rd Meeting	September 2022	D2.5; D2.6; D4.3; D8.4
4 th Meeting	March 2023	D4.4; D5.2; D8.5
5 th Meeting	September 2021	D4.5; D6.3; D8.6
6 th Meeting	March 2023	Final Report; D1.3; D2.8; D2.10; D3.8; D4.6; D8.7